

TEAM BUILDING INITIATIVES AS A TOOL IN INCREASING MOTIVATION AND EMPLOYEES' PRODUCTIVITY IN THE FOOD SERVICE SECTOR

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Abstract:

Successful teamwork doesn't work overnight, what makes teamwork potent is team building. (Plagiarism) According to Abdullah, et. al., (2022) team building training can improve group cohesiveness or the quality of sticking together or unity teamwork more likely to be higher with a significant score difference. This study used mixed methods both qualitative and quantitative data collection, and an analysis method to answer the research method, random sampling is named as such because the data set is chosen via random selection, where every member of the population has an equal probability of being selected (Tao, 2023). The respondents were 100 restaurant employees and 10 managers from the chosen restaurant in Malolos City in Bulacan. The subcategories of team building, including activities, communication, skills, personality, problem-solving, and values, have all received a consensus of strong agreement, with weighted averages falling within the range of 3.26 to 3.44. This level of agreement aligns with the scores for motivation at 3.43 and productivity at 3.38. These values have been calculated by determining the mean, which spans from 3.25 to 4.00. The advantages of team building that is being observed by the managers is to create familiarity and teamwork among the employees, to improve the quality of service and the quality of the food especially the respondents are in the food service sector, development, and training for the employees to achieve the establishments' goal and lastly rebuilding and build a relationship with one employee to another. However, for the disadvantages, it costs a lot of money to conduct team building in the management. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Despite the fact that there is a low correlation between teambuilding activities and motivation and employee productivity, there is still a significant relationship between the variables.

Keywords: *teambuilding initiatives, motivation, productivity, random sampling, food service sector, correlation*

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INTRODUCTION

Successful teamwork doesn't work overnight, what makes teamwork potent is team building. According to NJAGI in 2021, team building is routinely done by planning recreational activities where employees interact over games and workshops, among other activities that are geared towards this greater purpose. These activities serve to strengthen interpersonal relationships between people, which in turn allows them to appreciate the roles of their counterparts within their work institutions.

As stated by Abbas in 2021, collaboration's importance as a vital workplace tool often goes unnoticed by both employers and employees, leading to diminished performance and productivity. However, in line with Kashyap's findings in 2023, team-building games and activities not only influence how teams operate but also contribute to enhancing the overall personalities of individuals.

To some extent, motivated people enjoy their jobs in their workplace and give outstanding performance as compared to less motivated people. Studies and literature about team building focus on the ways that business owners can help workers to perform very well in the workplace. According to Berkeley People and Culture in 2023, the responsibility of a team builder is to steer the team towards cohesiveness and productivity. A team, over time, develops its own dynamic and requires consistent nurturing and maintenance to ensure its success. Team building has a positive contribution at work such as enhancing one's skills and creativity, strengthening relationships and bonds with co-workers, and initiating potential leaders to show their strength. (Peer Reviewer)

Additionally, as outlined by Kashyap in 2023, the fundamental concept behind team building is to empower individuals to collaborate toward shared objectives. The success of an organization hinges on its employees' capacity to function as a unified team, acknowledge each other's strengths and weaknesses, take an interest in one another's concerns, and collectively deliver the desired quality of work. There is substantial statistical and scientific evidence to demonstrate that team-building activities yield positive outcomes in the workplace. These activities are especially effective for teams seeking to enhance their collaborative dynamics and work together more effectively.

The importance of this study is to show that employee's productivity and motivation increase through the help of team-building initiatives. Present researchers lack the depth of knowledge to decipher the effects of team-building activities on employees' productivity and motivation. Also, numerous research studies have been conducted about the effects of team building on employee performance, but no one focused on employee productivity and motivation. In addition, most of the research and literature conducted focus on government, academic, and health sectors, but no one has conducted this research in the food sector. Furthermore, the literature, the researcher gathered are mostly international papers and no paper published locally.

The main objective of this research study is to identify the significance of teambuilding as a tool in increasing motivation and employee productivity in the food service sector in the City of Malolos in Bulacan. The overall purpose of this study is to provide research and recommendations on how organizations can assist in motivating and improving employee's productivity at selected restaurants in Malolos Bulacan. The study is therefore of importance to many individuals including

the food service sector who will become aware of the importance of team-building initiatives to increase motivation and employee productivity. The study may be beneficial to food service managers on learning how team building might affect motivation and employee productivity in their workplace.

Objectives:

Using a mixed method, this study aims to identify the significant effect and impact of team-building initiatives as a tool in increasing employees' productivity and motivation in the food service sector in Malolos, Bulacan.

This study aims to address the following specific questions:

1. How may the team building initiatives be described in terms of:

- 1.1 activity-based
- 1.2 communication-based
- 1.3 skills-based
- 1.4 personality-based
- 1.5 problem-solving-based
- 1.6 value-based

The various effects of team building can be identified in terms of:

- 2.1 motivation
- 2.2 productivity

What are the advantages and disadvantages of conducting team building in the food sector?

Is there a significant relationship between team-building activities and motivation and employees' productivity?

Methodology and Technique of the Study:

This study used mixed methods both qualitative and quantitative data collection, and an analysis method to answer the research method, random sampling is named as such because the data set is chosen via random selection, where every member of the population has an equal probability of being selected (Tao, 2023). The purpose of the method is to determine the significant effect and impact between teambuilding initiatives as a tool in increasing employee productivity and motivation in the food service sector in Malolos, Bulacan. The researchers have developed specific questions for both interview and survey questionnaires.

Furthermore, interviews and surveys are more effective in this study depending on the topic and respondents answering the questions.

The population of the study consists of restaurant employees and managers of ten (10) different restaurants around Malolos, Bulacan. The target number of employees and managers for each restaurant, ten (10) employees and managers of each restaurant were taken as a sample of the study. The respondents are chosen using random sampling techniques.

Restaurants in Malolos, Bulacan	Total number of Employees	Total number of Managers
Restaurant A	10	1
Restaurant B	10	1
Restaurant C	10	1
Restaurant D	10	1
Restaurant E	10	1
Restaurant F	10	1
Restaurant G	10	1
Restaurant H	10	1
Restaurant I	10	1
Restaurant J	10	1
Total Number of Respondents:	110	

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Food Service Managers and Employees as Respondents and Participants.

Research Instrument:

The questionnaire and interview questions are for food service managers and restaurant employees. The study used a self-constructed questionnaire according to research variables. The first twenty (20) items regarding teambuilding initiatives may be described in terms of activity-based, communication-based, skills-based, personality-based, problem-solving-based, and value-based, and the other twenty (20) regarding motivation and employees' productivity. Furthermore, the five (5) interview questions are prepared and modified by the researchers to measure the objectives effectively. In alignment with Morrison's research in 2023, questionnaire surveys serve as a valuable tool for collecting information from respondents across a diverse range of contexts. They are commonly employed for obtaining self-reported data in healthcare, understanding customer perspectives and satisfaction, as well as discerning product preferences in market research.

Also, the survey used to gather the information was validated by the research adviser and panel chair.

The test used in the study is the Likert scale. Indeed, as stated by Bhandari et al. in 2020, a Likert scale is a rating system employed for the purpose of measuring opinions, attitudes, or behaviors. These scales are known for their practicality and ease of use when it comes to collecting data. Typically, a Likert scale presents a statement or question, accompanied by a set of five or seven response options. Respondents then select the answer that most accurately reflects their feelings or stance regarding the given statement or question.

Data Gathering:

The study was conducted in a selected food service sector located in Malolos, Bulacan. The distribution used a purposive sampling technique in which the respondents were selected depending on the intent of the sample. Before administering the questionnaires, the researchers presented a letter that contained the intent of asking for their approval to be part of the

study. The information and data were strictly confidential and make sure that it will comply with the REPUBLIC ACT 10173 DATA PRIVACY ACT OF 2012, SEC. 2. Declaration of Policy. After the approval, the questionnaires were given to the respondents for them to answer and then be collected personally ensuring that safety protocols were implemented such as social distancing, wearing of face masks, and disinfecting while gathering the data.

Data Processing and Statistical Treatment

This part of the research would be the total tally of the gathered data that the researchers conducted through a surveyed form. It was divided into two categories: qualitative and quantitative procedures. Data processing in qualitative was the process of analyzing, interpreting, and organizing the answers conducted from the interview that would translate into accessible information.

Data processing in quantitative was the analysis used number-based or numerical information from the gathered data. The researchers used the Pearson correlation coefficient to prove the relationship between Teambuilding initiatives and motivation, and employee productivity. According to Turney in 2023, the Pearson correlation coefficient can also serve as a means to assess the significance of the relationship between two variables.

Furthermore, as per Glen's insights in 2023, a weighted mean is a type of average. It differs from the traditional arithmetic mean in that not all data points contribute equally to the final mean; some data points carry more "weight" than others. When all the weights are equal, the weighted mean is equivalent to the arithmetic mean, which is the common form of the average. Weighted means find frequent use in statistical analysis, particularly when studying populations.

Strongly Agree	3.26- 4.00
Agree	2.51- 3.25
Disagree	1.76- 2.50
Strongly Disagree	1.00- 1.75

Table 2. Likert scale for interpretation.

Result

Table 3. Frequency, Weighted Mean, and Descriptive Interpretation of Team Building Initiatives

Indicator	4	3	2	1	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Team Building promotes good relationship among employees.	62	38	0	1	3.39	Strongly Agree
2. Team Building fosters healthy relationships between the establishment and the employees.	54	46	0	0	3.54	Strongly Agree
3. Team Building outcomes incorporate the development of new skills and abilities among employees.	52	45	3	0	3.49	Strongly Agree
4. Team Building helps in Addressing the establishment's operational gaps	52	44	4	0	3.48	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean					3.48	Strongly Agree

As shown in Table 3, it shows how effective team building is for the employees. The first indicator got a weighted mean of 3.39 interpreted as Strongly Agree. The second indicator got a 3.54 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The third indicator got a 3.49 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree and the last indicator got a 3.48 weighted average interpreted as Strongly Agree. Therefore, most of the employees confirmed that the employees Strongly Agree that teambuilding initiatives are effective, similar to the findings of Hanaysha, J. (2016).

Table 4. Frequency, Weighted Mean and Descriptive Interpretation of Team Building Initiatives in terms of Activity-Based

Indicator	4	3	2	1	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. The restaurant staff continues to collaborate with the team during this time.	51	47	2	0	3.49	Strongly Agree
2. Team inspires every employee to work actively and do the best.	55	44	1	0	3.54	Strongly Agree
3. The employees feel comfortable contributing ideas and opinions during the team building	36	59	5	0	3.31	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean					3.44	Strongly Agree

As shown in Table 4, shows how effective teambuilding for the employees in terms of Activity-Based. The first indicator got a weighted mean of 3.49 interpreted as Strongly Agree. The second indicator got a 3.54 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree and the last indicator got a 3.31 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. Therefore, most of the employees confirmed that the employees Strongly Agree that teambuilding initiatives in terms of Activity-based are effective. Thus, this reflects the findings of Irkinovich, N. (2021).

Table 5. Frequency, Weighted Mean, and Descriptive Interpretation of Team Building Initiatives in terms of Communication-Based

Indicator	4	3	2	1	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. All employees feel comfortable asking for everyone's help in the team if do not have the skills required to meet the goals.	36	59	5	0	3.50	Strongly Agree
2. It is important to participate actively in the teamwork activity.	52	46	2	0	3.54	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean					3.44	Strongly Agree

As shown in Table 5, it shows how effective team building is for the employees in terms of communication. The first indicator got a weighted mean of 3.50 interpreted as Strongly Agree and the second indicator got a 3.54 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. It appears that the majority of employees have expressed strong agreement regarding the effectiveness of teambuilding initiatives in the context of Communication-Based approaches. This aligns with the view presented by Ali et al. in their work from 2021, which emphasizes that effective communication is a vital component of successful teamwork.

Table 6. Frequency, Weighted Mean, and Descriptive Interpretation of Team Building Initiatives in terms of Skills-Based

Indicator	4	3	2	1	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. It is important to keep the calmness in stressful situations at work.	60	40	0	0	3.60	Strongly Agree
2. It is important to be approachable when everyone's working in the team.	55	44	1	0	3.54	Strongly Agree
3. Team building makes all employees part of the team.	52	47	1	0	3.51	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean					3.55	Strongly Agree

As shown in table 6, it shows how effective teambuilding is for the employees in terms of Skill-Based. The first indicator got a weighted mean of 3.60 interpreted as Strongly Agree. The second indicator got a 3.54 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree and the last indicator got a 3.51 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. Therefore, most of the employees confirmed that the employees Strongly Agree that teambuilding initiatives in terms of Skill-based is effective. Whereas, Rodriguez, J. et al., (2023) mentioned that the development of skills for team building and performance is essential.

Table 7. Frequency, Weighted Mean, and Descriptive Interpretation of Team Building Initiatives in terms of Value-Based

Indicator	4	3	2	1	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Teambuilding has impact in the view of all employees on the company's value.	49	48	3	0	3.46	Strongly Agree
2. Teambuilding initiatives affects the employee's personal value.	42	53	5	0	3.37	Strongly Agree
3. Teambuilding initiatives helps the employees embodied the values of the company in their daily lives.	37	59	4	0	3.33	Strongly Agree
4. Participation and suggestions are very helpful in terms of finding a solution in the establishment.	55	44	1	0	3.54	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean					3.43	Strongly Agree

As shown in table 7, it shows how effective teambuilding is for the employees in terms of Value-Based. The first indicator got a weighted mean of 3.46 interpreted as Strongly Agree. The second indicator got a 3.37 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The third indicator got a 3.33 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree and the last indicator got a 3.54 weighted average interpreted as Strongly Agree. Therefore, most of the employees confirmed that the employees Strongly Agree that teambuilding initiatives in terms of Value-Based is effective, which was also mentioned by Irkinovich, N. (2021) in his study.

Table 8. Frequency, Weighted Mean, and Descriptive Interpretation of Team Building Initiatives in terms of Problem Solving-Based

Indicator	4	3	2	1	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Participating with an open mind/willingness enhances establishment and resolving its problem.	54	45	1	0	3.54	Strongly Agree
2. Some of employees prefer to work with the team.	33	61	6	0	3.27	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean					3.40	Strongly Agree

As shown in Table 8, it shows how effective team building is for the employees in terms of Problem Solving. The first indicator got a weighted mean of 3.54 interpreted as Strongly Agree and the second indicator got a 3.27 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. Therefore, most of the employees confirmed that they employees Strongly Agree that teambuilding initiatives in terms of Problem Solving- Based is effective. Similar to the findings of Guo et al., (2020), wherein he stated that through team building, people can get a chance to participate in real-world problem-solving and knowledge constructs.

Table 9. Frequency, Weighted Mean, and Descriptive Interpretation of Team Building Initiatives in terms of Personality-Based

Indicator	4	3	2	1	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Some of employees prefer to work individually/ alone.	27	61	12	0	3.15	Agree
2. The employees hold the same standards of performance in a given team task/s as also in individual.	40	56	4	0	3.36	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean					3.26	Strongly Agree

As shown in Table 9 shows how effective teambuilding is for the employees in terms of Personality-based. The first indicator got a weighted mean of 3.15 interpreted as Agree and the second indicator got a 3.36 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. Therefore, most of the employees confirmed that the employees Strongly Agree that teambuilding initiatives in terms of Personality-based is effective. Villanova University (2021), team building strategies that incorporate each team member’s personality type, with an understanding of how each individual interacts with others, can help businesses better appreciate what everyone has to offer.

Table 10. Frequency, Weighted Mean, and Descriptive Interpretation of Various Effects of Team Building in terms of Motivation

Indicator	4	3	2	1	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. The establishment conduct teambuilding activities for the employees.	40	59	1	0	3.39	Strongly Agree
2. Team building activities helps employees to become more motivated to work.	41	57	2	0	3.39	Strongly Agree
3. The employees are motivated after conducting a teambuilding.	37	60	3	0	3.34	Strongly Agree
4. The employees are motivated when the employees are satisfied.	44	56	0	0	3.44	Strongly Agree
5. The employees believe that teambuilding initiatives are important in increasing employee’s motivation.	48	50	2	0	3.46	Strongly Agree
6. Team building activities helps employees to strengthen the relationship with colleagues.	48	52	0	0	3.48	Strongly Agree
7. The employees believe that teambuilding initiative enables employees to become more motivated.	42	54	4	0	3.38	Strongly Agree
8. The employees believe that employees are more motivated when skills are acknowledged by colleagues and management	52	46	2	0	3.50	Strongly Agree
9. The employees believe that teambuilding activities increases the motivation and performance of the employees.	48	49	3	0	3.45	Strongly Agree
10. The employees believe that conducting teambuilding activities can help the establishment boost the employee’s motivation.	48	50	2	0	3.46	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean					3.43	Strongly Agree

As shown in table 10 shows how effective team building in terms of motivation for the employees. The first indicator got a weighted mean of 3.39 interpreted as Strongly Agree. The second indicator got a 3.39 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The third indicator got a 3.34 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The fourth indicator got a 3.44 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The fifth indicator got a 3.46 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The sixth indicator got a 3.48 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The seventh indicator got a 3.38 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The Eighth indicator got a 3.50 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The ninth indicator got a 3.45 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. and the last indicator got a 3.46 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. Therefore, most of the employees confirmed that the employees Strongly Agree on the Various effects of team building in terms of motivation. Machova et al. (2022) emphasized the importance of team-building programs in enhancing the employer-employee relationship, leading to increased employee motivation.

Table 11. Frequency, Weighted Mean, and Descriptive Interpretation of Various Effects of Team Building in terms of Productivity.

Indicator	4	3	2	1	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. The employees feel most productive after conducting teambuilding activities.	47	50	2	1	3.43	Strongly Agree
2. This organization is a good place for training and personal development	43	57	0	0	3.43	Strongly Agree
3. The employees believe that team building initiative enable employees to be more productive.	41	57	2	0	3.39	Strongly Agree
4. The employees feel that teambuilding activities encourage to be more productive.	44	54	2	0	3.42	Strongly Agree
5. The employees believe that team building initiatives contribute toward the better relationship between worker and management and increases productivity.	40	59	1	0	3.39	Strongly Agree
6. The employee's productivity comes out when collaborating with another co-worker.	34	64	2	0	3.32	Strongly Agree
7. The employees believe that there is a need of worker's involvement in production of an organization.	35	64	1	0	3.34	Strongly Agree
8. The team believe that conducting team building monthly is important for an employee's productivity	33	62	5	0	3.28	Strongly Agree
9. The team was more effective after a team building.	35	62	3	0	3.32	Strongly Agree
10. Being happy can lead to be more productive in workplace.	45	55	0	0	3.45	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean					3.38	Strongly Agree

As shown in table 11, shows how effective team building in terms of productivity. The first indicator got a weighted mean of 3.43 interpreted as Strongly Agree. The second indicator got a 3.43 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The third indicator got a 3.39 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The fourth indicator got a 3.42 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The fifth indicator got a 3.39 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The sixth indicator got a 3.32 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The seventh indicator got a 3.34 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The Eighth indicator got a 3.28 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. The ninth indicator got a 3.32 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. and the last indicator got a 3.45 weighted mean interpreted as Strongly Agree. Therefore, most of the employees confirmed that the employees Strongly Agree that various effect of team building in terms of productivity is effective. Thus, team building has a positive impact on the teams' outcomes (Salas et al., 2005; Klein, 2009; Efimova & Kokurin, 2014).

Table 12. Result of the Significance Test

T-value	a	T computed	Conclusion
1.984	0.05	2.569	Reject the null hypothesis

Therefore, there exists a small and low correlation between team building, motivation, and productivity.

Discussion of Findings

The researchers gathered data about the significant effect and relationship between team building initiatives to motivation, and employees’ productivity. With regards to this, most of the respondents strongly agreed in terms of questionnaires for the employees. Team building subtopics are all interpreted as strongly agreeing that the weighted mean ranges from 3.26-3.44 same with motivation 3.43 and for productivity 3.38 that is based on a computation in finding the mean which is from 3.25-4.00.

It also shows the advantages of team building that is being observed by the managers to create familiarity and teamwork among the employees, to improve the quality of service and the quality of the food especially the respondents are in the food service sector, development, and training for the employees to achieve the establishments’ goal and lastly rebuilding and build a relationship with one employee to another. According to Sharma, 2023, teambuilding can help build strong relationships among coworkers, increase team morale, and even allow team members to learn new skills. In short, team-building activities at work are essential for any manager who wants their employees to work together effectively.

The disadvantage, it costs a lot of money to conduct team building in the management. According to Robinson, 2022, team building requires investment. Cost is one team-building disadvantage and one reason that organizations shy away from commitment.

Conclusion

The conclusion $r= 0.228$ results in a low or weak correlation between teambuilding activities and motivation and employee productivity. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Despite the fact that there is a low correlation between teambuilding activities and motivation and employee productivity, there is still a significant relationship between the variables.

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